
Awareness and Need to Preserve “Traditional Indian Knowledge”

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Abstract:

Traditional Indian Knowledge (TIK) includes types of the knowledge relates to cultural, scientific, and philosophical insights developed over millennia, including fields such as Ayurveda, Vedic mathematics, traditional crafts, and oral literature. Despite its historical significance and practical value, TIK faces substantial threats from modernization, globalization, and cultural erosion. This paper investigates the current level of awareness about TIK and need for its preservation.

The paper argues that preserving TIK is essential for maintaining cultural heritage, promoting sustainable practices, enriching modern scientific and medical knowledge. To take the advantage of own TIK, one must be aware of it and aware about the need to preserve it. In this regards the researcher not only collects primary data mainly from the students and the teachers of commerce faculty, but also takes the help of books, websites and other published sources to come to the final conclusion.

Keywords: *Traditional Indian Knowledge.*

Introduction:

TIK plays a significant role in the development of the society and the nation. It reflects from the rich cultural, philosophical, scientific and artistic heritage of India. It includes the things like Philosophy and Spirituality (Vedanta, Yoga, Ayurveda), Mathematics and Astronomy (Zero and the Decimal System), Science and Technology (Historical Material, Engineering Science and Architecture), Literature and Arts (Epics, Classical Dance and Music), Agriculture and Ecology (Farming techniques), Traditional Craftsmanship (Textiles and Handicrafts) and so on. Preserving such kind of the traditional knowledge ensures that valuable practices and insights continue to benefit individuals and society in the future. It is necessary and need to honours cultural identity and values for future generation.

With the development of industries

globalization and privatization takes place. In this competitive environment every individual, manufacturer, seller wants to earn profit and will becomes a successful business men/ women. Society expects ethical business practices from such business persons. But unfortunately very few business men/women involved in it. Some business persons involved in unethical practices by claiming others traditional practices and knowledge as its own. In order to restrain such persons, one must know their own traditional knowledge, culture and heritage.

Objectives:

- 1 To study the awareness about the TIK among students and teachers.
- 2 To study the need to preserve the TIK.

Relevancy of Study:

In order to face the competition and earn the huge profit, in the current business environment, lots of persons, manufactures, and sellers adopts unethical business practices. They claim and copy products, services as well as knowledge of others. To restrict such things, there must be some rules, laws and regulatory authorise. But before that one must be aware about their own rights over such products, services, and knowledge. For creating new rules and laws there is a need to check the awareness of TIK among the people in the society. This is the basic aim of this research study.

Data Collection:

Primary data for the purpose of the present study is collected by the researcher from students and teachers. For this purpose structured questionnaire is prepared by the researcher. By making Google form such questions were asked by the researcher to the respondents. And Secondary data is collected from various web sites, books and other published sources.

1. Sample Size:

By adopting Convenient sampling method, the researcher collect data from students and teachers in the commerce faculty of KANMS Arts, Science and Commerce College, Satana, District Nashik in the state of Maharashtra. Data is collected from total 54 respondents.

2. Scope of the Study:

Present research was conducted in the Commerce Faculty of KANMS Arts, Science and Commerce College - Satana, in Nashik district in the state of Maharashtra.

3. Limitation of Study:

First limitation: Present research was conducted only to find out the awareness and need to preserve traditional Indian knowledge.

Second Limitation: Data collected for the

current research was from the students and faculty members in the commerce faculty in KANMS Arts, Science and Commerce College - Satana, in Nashik district.

Third Limitation: Data is collected from 54 respondents in which 90.4% respondents are students and remaining 9.6% are the teachers in commerce faculty.

Fourth Limitation: This research is conducted in the month of August 2024.

Awareness about Traditional Indian Knowledge:

As we all know in order to protect our own rights, we first aware of those rights. To know whether the students and teachers are aware about TIK, the researcher makes a Structured Questionnaire. Questions below are the part of that questionnaire.

- 1 Do you know about the - Ayurveda, Yoga, Vedic Sciences, Indian Philosophy, Traditional Arts and Crafts, Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Traditional Architecture, Language and Literature, Religious Practices and Rituals, Social and Ethical Systems?
- 2 Does the TIK giving subjects included earlier in your syllabus?
- 3 Do you know about the laws to protect the TIK all over the India?
- 4 Do you think these things are the important thing, in today's competitive world?
- 5 Is learning the TIK giving subjects will beneficial to you in near future?
- 6 In Future, among TIK giving subjects, which subject you, will like to study?
- 7 Are you interested to learn TIK giving subjects of other country?

Need to Preserve the Traditional Indian Knowledge:

There are various reasons, which indicate the need to preserve and protect the TIK. From the view point of the current research to know such reasons, opinion of students and teachers are important. For this

the researcher intentionally involved the following questions in their questionnaire.

- 1 Do you know the benefits of preserving TIK?
- 2 Is it Essential to Preserve and Protect these TIK?
- 3 Does learning TIK giving subjects will increase your earnings?

Other Reasons:

1. Protecting Indigenous culture and identities: Traditional knowledge and languages are a significant way to maintain and preserve Indigenous cultures and identities and promote well-being.

2. Protecting livelihoods: Traditional knowledge is one of the sources of livelihood for indigenous people, which must be protected.

3. Health benefits: As traditional

knowledge is connected with environment and spirituality, they are important to well-being. Further, traditional medicines can provide health benefits to a large population in India

4. Ecological benefits: Traditional knowledge presents enormous opportunities to conserve forests and biodiversity. For example, sacred groves or forest temples are one of the methods to conserve biodiversity. Indigenous people and their traditional methods have been beneficial in conserving biodiversity, for example, the Maldhari tribe of Gujarat and the Bishnois of Rajasthan.

5. Attaining Sustainable Development Goals: It may provide helpful solutions to issues like tackling inequality, combating climatechange, and food insecurity, among others, that we are attempting to address through the Sustainable Development Goals.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

1.9.1

Out of 54 respondents, 9.3% respondents are teachers and remaining 90.4% are the students in Commerce faculty.

1.9.2

88.9% respondents know about the - Ayurveda, Yoga, Vedic Sciences, Indian Philosophy, Traditional Arts and Crafts, Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Traditional Architecture, Language and Literature, Religious Practices and Rituals, Social and Ethical Systems.

1.9.3

64.8% respondents respond that Traditional Indian knowledge giving subjects included earlier in their syllabus.

1.9.11

Out of 54 respondents 39 (72.2%) are interested to learn Traditional Knowledge giving subjects of other country.

1.9.4

74.1% respondents know the benefits of Ayurveda, Yoga, Vedic Sciences, Indian Philosophy, Traditional Arts and Crafts, Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Traditional Architecture, Language and Literature, Religious Practices and Rituals, Social and Ethical Systems

Conclusion:

At the end of this research, the researcher is of the opinion that majority of the respondents is aware about the TIK (88.9%) as such TIK giving subjects are the part of their syllabus (64.8%) earlier.

74.1% respondents know the advantages and 94.9% know the importance of TIK.

90.7% respondents are of the opinion that studying the TIK giving subjects will increase their earnings and 79.6% says they will get monetary benefits in future.

That's why not only 22.2% and 14.8% respondents are interested to learn Traditional Art and Yoga in near future but also 72.2% respondents are interested to learn the traditional knowledge giving subjects of other country.

In order to Protecting Indigenous culture and identities, Restrict – Bio-piracy, Protecting livelihoods, Health, Ecological benefits and for Attaining Sustainable Development Goals and spreading the awareness about the laws to protect TIK

(because 59.3% respondents are not aware of the laws to protect the – TIK)

It is the opinion of 92.6% respondents that it is important to preserve, protect and spread awareness of laws which protect TIK for future generation.

In order to protect indigenous culture and identities, protecting livelihoods, gain knowledge about health, ecological benefits and to attend sustainable development goals, there is a need to spreading awareness about TIK.

References:

- 1 <https://vajiramandravi.com/quest-upsc-notes/traditional-knowledge/>